

Monomeric and dimeric stilbenoids from the orchid *Dendrobium amplum*

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Abstract : Amplumthrin, a new dimeric 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative, was isolated from the orchid *Dendrobium amplum* which also afforded the known 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene dimer flavanthrin and the monomeric stilbenoids gigantol, batatasin III, its 3'-O-methyl ether and 3,3'-O,O-dimethyl ether, 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene and its 9,10-dihydro derivative, 2,3,7-trihydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyphenanthrene and its 9,10-dihydro derivative and coelonin. The structure of amplumthrin was established as 2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-3,3',4,4',6,6'-hexamethoxy-9,9',10,10'-tetrahydro-1,1'-biphenanthryl from various spectral and chemical evidence. The structure of amplumthrin was finally confirmed by regioselective biomimetic synthesis of the compound from its monomeric congener 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene by oxidative phenol-coupling reaction with CuCl(OH).TMEDA in very good yield (80%). Similar biomimetic synthesis of flavanthrin was also achieved in 82% yield from its monomeric congener coelonin using the same oxidant. The co-occurrence of amplumthrin and flavanthrin with their respective monomers in the same orchid *Dendrobium amplum* provides a strong circumstantial evidence in support of the proposed biogenesis of the naturally occurring biphenanthryl derivatives assumed to have arisen from their corresponding monomers through enzymatic oxidative phenol-coupling reaction.

Keywords : *Dendrobium amplum*, orchidaceae, amplumthrin, flavanthrin, dimeric 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivatives, biomimetic synthesis, oxidative phenol-coupling reaction with CuCl(OH).TMEDA.

Introduction

We reported earlier the isolation of a fairly large number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These phytochemicals encompass a wide variety of stilbenoids, viz. stilbene¹, bibenzyls², phenanthrenes and 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes^{3,4} and their dimers⁵⁻⁷, phenanthropyrans and pyrones and their 9,10-dihydroderivatives⁸⁻¹², fluorenones¹³ and a few other polyphenolics^{14,15}, several triterpenoids¹⁶⁻¹⁸, steroids of biogenetic importance¹⁹⁻²¹ and some simple aromatic compounds²². As part of this general programme of research we have chemically investigated yet another Indian orchid *Dendrobium amplum*. This has resulted in the isolation of a new dimeric 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative, designated amplumthrin, besides gigantol²³ (**1a**), batatasin III²⁴ (**1b**), its 3'-O-methylether²⁵ (**1c**) and 3,3'-O,O-dimethylether²⁶ (**1d**), 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene²⁷ (**2a**) and its 9,10-dihydro derivative²⁷ (**2b**), 2,3,7-trihydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy phenanthrene²⁸ (**2d**) and its 9,10-dihydro derivative²⁹ (**2e**), coelonin⁴ (**2f**), flavanthrin⁷ (**3c**) and β -sitosterol of previously known structures. While the known compounds were

characterized by comparison with their respective authentic samples and reported spectral data and in some cases independent spectral analysis, the structure of amplumthrin was established as 2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-3,3',4,4',6,6'-hexamethoxy-9,9',10,10'-tetrahydro-1,1'-biphenanthryl (**3a**) from spectral and chemical evidence, and was finally confirmed by its regioselective biomimetic synthesis from its monomeric congener **2b** by oxidative phenol-coupling reaction with CuCl(OH).TMEDA^{30,31} (TMEDA = Me₂N-(CH₂)₂-NMe₂) in very good yield (80%). Similar regioselective biomimetic synthesis of flavanthrin (**3c**) was also achieved from its congener coelonin (**2f**) in about 82% yield using the above oxidant.

Results and discussion

Amplumthrin (**3a**), amorph. [α]_D³⁰ -15°(c, 0.125, MeOH), analyzed for C₃₄H₃₄O₁₀ which was confirmed by its mass spectrometrically derived molecular weight 602. The UV absorptions of the compound, $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 219, 275 and 304 nm (log ϵ 4.65, 4.50 and 4.01) strikingly resemble those of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivatives^{7,27}. The phenolic nature of **3a** was indicated by its

characteristic colour reactions, alkali-induced bathochromic shifts of its UV maxima $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH } 0.1 \text{ M NaOH}}$ 230, 279 and 310 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.55, 4.60 and 4.33) and by its IR absorption at ν_{\max} 3421 cm^{-1} . The presence of four phenolic hydroxyl groups in **3a** was confirmed by the formation of its tetraacetyl derivative, $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_{14}$ ($[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 770), amorph., with Ac_2O and pyridine.

The 500 MHz ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) spectrum of **3a** showed nine sets of signals at δ 7.97, 6.75, 5.62, 5.59, 4.03, 3.94, 3.82, 2.48–2.58 and 2.27–2.43 in the integral ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 2 : 2. Since **3a** contains 34 protons, each of these signals thus corresponds to double the number of protons given by their respective integral ratio. This, in turn, also implied the symmetrical dimeric formulation of the compound. Thus, the two two-proton broad signals at δ 5.62 and 5.59 (each disappeared on deuterium exchange) in the ^1H NMR spectrum of **3a** indicated the presence of four phenolic hydroxyl groups in the compound, while the three six-proton singlets at δ 4.03, 3.94 and 3.82 corresponded to three pairs of aromatic methoxyl functions, each pair being in identical environment. The spectrum of **3a** showed two different sets of aromatic proton signals at δ 7.97 and 6.75 (each 2H, s). The signal at δ 7.97 is typical of H-5 or H-4 of a 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative⁴. The assignment of this signal appearing as a two-proton singlet to H-5 and H-5' of **3a** would require C-6, C-6' and C-7, C-7' of the compound to be substituted by OMe/OH. The other aromatic proton signal of **3a** at δ 6.75 would then correspond to H-8 and H-8' of the compound. The striking similarities of the chemical shifts and splitting patterns of the above aromatic protons of amplumthrin [δ 7.97 and 6.75 (each 2H, s)] and its tetraacetate (**3b**) [δ 8.11 and 6.88 (each 2H, s)] with H-5 and H-8 of 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene (**2b**) [δ 7.93 and 6.81 (each 1H, s)] and its diacetate (**2c**) [δ 8.10 and 6.91 (each 1H, s)], respectively, not only established the structural identity of ring A and A' of amplumthrin with the ring A of **2b**, but also ruled out the possibility of any linkage of the two monomeric halves through any carbon atom of this part of amplumthrin. The absence of any downfield proton signal around δ 8.0 other than that for H-5 and H-5' (δ 7.97) in amplumthrin implied the substituted nature of C-4 and C-4' of the compound. In the light of the observation³² that H-5 of a 4-hydroxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative shows an upfield shift in the ^1H NMR spectrum of its acetyl derivative, the downfield shift of H-5' and H-5' (δ 8.11) of

amplumthrin tetraacetate (**3b**) ruled out the placement of hydroxyl groups at C-4 and C-4' of amplumthrin. This, in turn, implied the placement of methoxyl groups at C-4 and C-4' of the compound. The absence of the aromatic proton signal corresponding to that of H-1 of **2b** (δ 6.65) and **2c** (δ 6.73) in the ^1H NMR spectra of amplumthrin and its tetraacetate (**3b**), respectively, indicated the site of dimerization in amplumthrin to be at the 1,1'-position with the remaining two hydroxyl groups and the two methoxyl functions located at C-2 and C-2' and C-3 and C-3' positions, respectively. The most convincing evidence for the 1,1'-coupling in amplumthrin was provided by the nonequivalence of H₂-10/H₂-10' and H₂-9/H₂-9' of both amplumthrin (**3a**) and its tetraacetate (**3b**), and the relatively up field shift of two of the four acetate methyl protons of **3b**. The H₂-9 and H₂-10 of most of the monomeric 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivatives were found to resonate as four-proton singlet as in **2b**, **2c**, **2e** and **2f**, while in the ^1H NMR spectra of **3a** and **3b** these protons resonated as two four-proton multiplets at δ 2.27–2.43 and 2.48–2.58 and δ 2.27–2.40 and 2.51–2.55, respectively. Further, the methyl protons of two of the four acetoxy functions in **3b** resonated at a relatively upfield position (δ 1.99) compared to the other two acetate methyls which appeared at the normal position (δ 2.34) as in **2c**. These observations can only be rationalized in terms of a 1,1'-coupling of two units of **2b** in amplumthrin as in **3a** and similar formulation of **3b** for its tetraacetate. Construction of Dreiding models of **3a** and **3b** shows that in the most preferred conformations of the two molecules, the two monomeric halves remain almost perpendicular to each other so that H₂-10 and H₂-10' fall in the shielding zone of the neighbouring aromatic rings C' and C, respectively and this accounts for the observed upfield shifts of these protons in **3a** and **3b**. The rings C' and C also exert a long range shielding effect on H₂-9 and H₂-9', which appeared at a relatively less upfield position than H₂-10 and H₂-10'. The methyl protons of the two acetoxy groups at C-2 and C-2' of **3b** likewise fall in the shielding zones of the rings C' and C, respectively, and as a result they are shifted up field (δ 1.99) compared to those of the other two acetate methyls which appear at the normal region (δ 2.34). This type of diamagnetic anisotropic effect of the neighbouring aromatic rings of the methyl protons of the acetoxy functions attached to the carbon atoms *ortho* to the site of coupling is a well documented feature of similar biaryl derivatives⁷.

The structure **3a** for amplumthrin was further corroborated by the ^{13}C NMR spectral data of the com-

1a : $R^1 = H, R^2 = Me, R^3 = OH$

1b : $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = H$

1c : $R^1 = R^3 = H, R^2 = Me$

1d : $R^1 = R^2 = Me, R^3 = H$

2a : $R^1 = R^4 = H, R^2 = R^3 = OMe, 9,10$ -dehydro-

2b : $R^1 = R^4 = H, R^2 = R^3 = OMe, 9,10$ -dihydro-

2c : $R^1 = R^4 = Ac, R^2 = R^3 = OMe, 9,10$ -dihydro-

2d : $R^1 = R^4 = H, R^2 = OH, R^3 = OMe, 9,10$ -dehydro-

2e : $R^1 = R^4 = H, R^2 = OH, R^3 = OMe, 9,10$ -dihydro-

2f : $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = H, 9,10$ -dihydro-

compound and its tetraacetate **3b** (Table 1). The degree of protonation of each carbon atom was determined by DEPT experiments and the assignments of the carbon chemical shifts of **3a** and **3b** were made by comparison of the δ_C values with those of **2b** and **2c**, respectively, and other structurally related compounds. The ^{13}C NMR spectra of both **3a** and **3b** exhibited 17 and 21 carbon signals, respectively. These numbers are just half of the number of carbon atoms present in their respective molecular formulae. This is again in conformity with their symmetrical dimeric formulation. Further, except for C-1 and C-1' and C-10 and C-10', the signals for all the carbon atoms of **3a** and **3b** appeared essentially at the same positions as those for the corresponding carbon atoms of **2b** and **2c**, respectively. The signals for the protonated C-1 of **2b** (δ_C 110.2) and **2c** (δ_C 117.3) are replaced by the relatively down field nonprotonated carbon signals at δ_C 116.5 and 123.7 in the spectra of **3a** and **3b**, respectively. This is another convincing evidence that amplumthrin is a symmetrical dimer of its monomeric congener **2b** linked at

its C-1. The upfield shift of C-10 and C-10' of **3a** and **3b** by about 2–3 ppm compared to their C-9 and C-9', which finds strong analogy with similar upfield shifts of C-10 in 1-substituted 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivatives⁸ and those of C-10 and C-10' of 1,1'-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene dimers⁷ provides further evidence for the 1,1'-dimeric formulation for amplumthrin (**3a**).

More compelling evidence in support of the structure **3a** for amplumthrin was provided by the 2D NMR spectral analysis (HMOC and HMBC with J_{C-H} parameters set to 160 Hz and 7 Hz, respectively) of the more soluble amplumthrin tetraacetate (**3b**) and the corresponding monomeric diacetate (**2c**). The chemical shifts of all the pro-

3a : $R^1 = R^4 = H, R^2 = R^3 = OMe$

3b : $R^1 = R^4 = Ac, R^2 = R^3 = OMe$

3c : $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = H$

tonated carbon atoms of both **2c** and **3b** (Table 1) were confirmed by the 1-bond $^1H-^{13}C$ correlations observed in the HMOC spectra of these compounds, while the long range (3-bond and in a few cases 2-bond) $^1H-^{13}C$ correlations exhibited by the HMBC spectra of both **2c** and **3b** further confirmed the assignments of their protonated as well as nonprotonated carbon atoms. In the HMBC spectra, the strongest correlations are those between 3-bond, while 2-bond and rarely 4-bond correlations are also sometimes observed in compounds containing oxygenated functions like methoxy and hydroxy/acetoxo attached to the aromatic ring, which presumably alter the electron distribution in favour of such couplings³². Thus, the most downfield proton at δ_H 8.10 assigned to H-5 of **2c** showed three strong 3-bond and one 2-bond fairly strong correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_C 125.7, 138.2, 130.8, and 149.1 attributed to C-4a, C-7, C-8a and C-6, respectively. Similarly, the corresponding aromatic proton at δ_H 8.11 (H-5 and H-5') of **3b** also showed three strong 3-bond and one 2-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_C 125.9, 138.4, 131.5 and 149.1, which may,

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of **2b**, **3a**, **2c**, **3b**, **2f** and **3c**

C	Chemical shifts (δ ppm)					
	2b [†]	3a [†]	2c [†]	3b [†]	2f ^{††}	3c ^{††}
1 (1')	110.2 ^a	116.5	117.3	123.7	108.0	113.2
2 (2')	147.4	145.6	142.6	141.4	158.8 ^a	155.3 ^e
3 (3')	138.9	138.8	144.1	144.3	99.1	98.8
4 (4')	150.2	149.9	151.7	151.2	158.5	158.0
4a (4a')	120.3	120.7	125.7	125.9	116.1	116.8
4b (4b')	124.4	124.6	130.2	130.4	125.5	125.8
5 (5')	110.3 ^a	110.6	112.4	112.8	129.6	129.8
6 (6')	143.8	143.9	149.1	149.1	114.7 ^b	114.4 ^f
7 (7')	144.8	144.7	138.2	138.4	157.1 ^a	155.8 ^e
8 (8')	113.6	113.3	121.5	121.4	113.3 ^b	114.2 ^f
8a (8a')	131.3	131.6	130.8	131.5	141.0 ^c	140.9 ^g
9 (9')	30.1	28.8	28.3	28.3	30.5 ^d	30.0
10 (10')	28.9	26.6	29.5	26.3	31.0 ^d	27.6
10a (10a')	135.0	134.4	134.6	134.7	139.7 ^c	139.9 ^g
OMe	56.1	56.1	55.9	56.1	55.5	55.4
	(OMe at C-6)	(OMe at C-6, C-6')	(OMe at C-6)	(OMe at C-6, C-6')		
	60.0	60.2	60.3	60.5	—	—
			(OMe at C-3)	(OMe at C-3, C-3')		
	61.1	61.2	60.7	60.9	—	—
			(OMe at C-4)	(OMe at C-4, C-4')		
OCOMe	—	—	169.0, 20.5	169.1, 20.6	—	—
	—	—	—	168.4, 20.1		

[†]Spectra were run in CDCl_3 and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(\text{CDCl}_3)} + 76.9$ ppm.

^{††}Spectra were run in d_6 -acetone and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta(d_6\text{-acetone}) + 29.6$ ppm.

^{a-g}Values are interchangeable in each column.

therefore, be assigned to C-4a (C-4a'), C-7 (C-7'), C-8a (C-8a') and C-6 (C-6'), respectively, of **3b**. The HMBC spectrum of **2c** also showed, in addition, a weak 4-bond correlation between the proton at δ_{H} 8.10 with the carbon resonance at δ_{C} 28.3 which may be assigned to C-9 of **2c**. This correlation is, however, absent in the spectrum of **3b**. The proton at δ_{H} 6.91 assigned to H-8 of **2c** exhibited three strong 3-bond and one 2-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_{C} 130.2, 149.1, 28.3 and 138.2, which are thus assigned to C-4b, C-6, C-9 and C-7, respectively, of **2c**. Similarly, the proton at δ_{H} 6.88 assigned to H-8 (H-8') of **3b** showed three strong 3-bond and one 2-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_{C} 130.4, 149.1, 28.3 and 138.4, which may likewise be assigned to C-4b (C-4b'), C-6 (C-6'), C-9 (C-9') and C-7 (C-7'), respectively, of **3b**. The protons at δ_{H} 2.70 of **2c** attributed to H₂-9 and H₂-10 displayed six strong 3-

bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_{C} 121.5, 130.2, 134.6, 117.3, 125.7 and 130.8, which were assigned to C-8, C-4b, C-10a, C-1, C-4a, and C-8a, respectively, of the compound. But H₂-9 (H₂-9') and H₂-10 (H₂-10') of **3b** are not equivalent. The relatively downfield methylene protons at δ_{H} 2.51–2.55 of **3b** corresponding to H₂-9 (H₂-9') exhibited three 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_{C} 130.4, 121.4 and 134.7, which corresponded to C-4b (C-4b'), C-8 (C-8') and C-10a (C-10a'), respectively, while the relatively upfield methylene protons at δ_{H} 2.27–2.40, which were attributed to H₂-10 (H₂-10') showed three 3-bond and one 2-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_{C} 123.7, 125.9, 131.5 and 134.7, which corresponded to C-1 (C-1'), C-4a (C-4a'), C-8a (C-8a') and C-10a (C-10a'), respectively. The 3-bond correlation of the methylene protons at δ_{H} 2.27–2.40 [H₂-10 (H₂-10')] with the

nonprotonated carbons at δ_C 123.7 [C-1 (C-1')] as stated above, in particular, implied the 1,1'-dimeric formulation of **3b** and hence of **3a**. The methoxyl protons at δ_H 3.87 of **2c** and those at δ_H 3.89 of **3b** showed 1-bond correlations with the relatively upfield carbon resonances at δ_C 55.9 and 56.1 of **2c** and **3b**, respectively, due to having at least one *ortho* hydrogen atom. These methoxyl groups must, therefore, be attached to C-6 of **2c** and C-6 (C-6') of **3b**. The protons of these methoxyl groups of both **2c** and **3b** exhibited strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonance at δ_C 149.1 of both the compounds, which corresponded to C-6 of **2c** and C-6 (C-6') of **3b**. Other methoxyl protons at δ_H 3.91 and 3.77 of **2c**, which showed 1-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_C 60.7 and 60.3, respectively, exhibited 3-bond correlations with the nonprotonated carbons at δ_C 151.7 and 144.1. These were assigned to C-4 and C-3, respectively, of **2c**. This is evident from the fact that the proton at δ_C 6.73 assigned to H-1 of **2c** showed three strong 3-bond, one 2-bond and a weak 4-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_C 144.1, 125.7, 29.5, 142.6, and 151.7, respectively, which corresponded to C-3, C-4a, C-10, C-2 and C-4 of the compound. Similarly, the protons at δ_C 3.94 and 3.83

of **3b** which showed 1-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_C 60.9 and 60.5, respectively, exhibited 3-bond correlations with carbons at δ_C 144.3 and 151.2. By analogy with similar correlations observed in **2c**, the above two carbon resonances of **3b** were assigned to C-3 (C-3') and C-4 (C-4'), respectively, and the carbon signal at δ_C 141.4 of **3b** was attributed to C-2 (C-2'). The correlations observed in the HMBC spectra of **2c** and **3b** as shown on their respective structural diagrams thus further confirmed their assigned structures.

The structure of amplumthrin (**3a**) was finally confirmed by a regioselective biomimetic synthesis of the compound from its congener monomer **2b** by oxidative phenol-coupling reaction with $\text{CuCl}(\text{OH}) \cdot \text{TMEDA}$, CH_2Cl_2 , TMEDA ^{30,31} in 80% yield (Scheme 1). Attempted conversion of **2b** to **3a** with phosphomolybdic acid (PMA) on silica gel surface³³ earlier led to the formation of 9,9',10,10'-tetrahydro derivative of **3a**, instead of **3a** itself. It has been observed³³ that in the reaction of 2,7-dihydroxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivatives having OH and/or OMe groups at C-3 and/or C-6 with PMA on silica gel surface the rate of dehydrogenation is much faster than oxidative coupling. As a result such 9,10-dihydrophenanthrols are

Scheme 1. Biomimetic synthesis of **3a** and **3c**.

first dehydrogenated to the corresponding monomeric phenanthrols which then undergo oxidative coupling to the corresponding phenanthrene dimers. On the other hand, 2,7-dihydroxy-4-methoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivatives having no OH and or OMe groups at C-3 and or C-6 on oxidation with PMA on silica gel surface gave directly the corresponding 1,1'-dimer. Thus, coelonin (**2f**) on treatment with PMA on silica gel surface earlier³³ gave flavanthrin (**3c**) in very good yield (80%). We have now accomplished another regioselective biomimetic synthesis of **3c** from its monomeric congener **2f** in 82% yield by oxidative coupling with CuCl(OH).TMEDA (Scheme 1). Thus, while with PMA on silica gel surface **2b** gave 9,9',10,10'-tetrahydro derivative of **3a** and **2f** afforded **3c**, respectively and with CuCl(OH).TMEDA both **2b** and **2f** afforded their respective 1,1'-dimers.

Amplumthrin (**3a**) is thus a new addition to the growing list of the naturally occurring dimeric phenanthrene derivatives. The cooccurrence of amplumthrin (**3a**) and flavanthrin (**3c**) with their respective monomers **2b** and coelonin (**2f**) in the same orchid *Dendrobium amplum* provides a strong circumstantial evidence for the biogenesis of naturally occurring dimeric phenanthrene derivatives from their respective phenolic monomers by oxidative phenol-coupling reaction.

Experimental

M.p.s. : uncorr. CC : silica gel (100–200 mesh). TLC : silica gel G. IR : KBr discs. ¹H and ¹³C NMR : 300 MHz/500 MHz and 75 MHz/125 MHz, respectively. NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ using TMS as int. standard. Chemical shifts were expressed in δ (ppm). The HMQC and HMBC spectra of amplumthrin tetraacetate (**3b**) and the acetyl derivative of **2b** (**2c**) were recorded with J_{C-H} parameters set to 160 Hz and 7 Hz, respectively. MS : direct inlet system, 70 eV. All analyt. samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. The petrol used had b.p. 60–80 °C. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was used for drying organic solvents.

Plant materials :

Dendrobium amplum Lindl. was collected from Kalimpong (Darjeeling, India) in October 2003. A voucher specimen (Majumder s.n.) was deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, University of Calcutta (CUH).

Isolation of amplumthrin (3a), 3c, 1a, 1b, 1c, 1d, 2a, 2b, 2d, 2e and 2f :

Air-dried finely powdered whole plant of *D. amplum*

(4.5 kg) was kept soaked in MeOH (10 ml) for 4 weeks. The MeOH extract was concentrated to ca. 100 ml, diluted with H₂O (750 ml) and exhaustively extracted with Et₂O. The Et₂O extract was fractionated into acidic and non-acidic fractions with 2 M NaOH. The aq. alkaline soln. was acidified in the cold with conc. HCl and the liberated solids were extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The Et₂O extract containing the non-acidic constituents (left after treatment with 2 M NaOH) was also washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residues containing the acidic and non-acidic (neutral) compounds were separately chromatographed.

Chromatography of the acidic fraction :

The petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate afforded a mixture of batatasin-III-3'-O-methyl ether (**1c**), 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy phenanthrene (**2a**) and its 9,10-dihydroderivative (**2b**), which on rechromatography using the same solvent gave pure **1c** (0.05 g) as a semi-solid mass in the early fractions. The later fractions of the same eluate gave a mixture of **2a** and **2b**. Repeated chromatography of the above mixture using the same eluent afforded pure **2a** (0.06 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 145 °C, in the early fractions and pure **2b** (0.08 g) in the later fractions, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 114 °C; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.93 (1H, s, H-5), 6.81 (1H, s, H-8), 6.65 (1H, s, H-1), 5.79 (2H, br. signal, disappeared on deuterium exchange, Ar-OH), 3.99, 3.93 and 3.76 (each 3H, s, Ar-OMe) and 2.67 (4H, s, H₂-9 and H₂-10).

Acetylation of **2b** with Ac₂O and pyridine in the usual manner afforded the corresponding diacetyl derivative **2c**, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 111 °C ; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.10 (1H, s, H-5), 6.91 (1H, s, H-8), 6.73 (1H, s, H-1), 3.91 (3H, s, OMe at C-4), 3.87 (3H, s, OMe at C-6) and 3.77 (3H, s, OMe at C-3), 2.70 (4H, s, H₂-9 and H₂-10) and 2.34 and 2.33 (each 3H, s, Ar-OAc).

Elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (20 : 1) afforded a gummy mixture of gigantol (**1a**), batatasin-III (**1b**) and coelonin (**2f**). Rechromatography of this gummy mixture using the same eluent gave in the early fractions pure **1a** (0.4 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 95 °C. The later fractions of the same eluate afforded a mixture of **1b** and **2f**, which on rechromatography gave pure **1b** (0.2 g) in the early fractions, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 94 °C and coelonin (**2f**) as an amorphous solid in the later fractions.

Elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) afforded a gummy solid containing a mixture of 2,3,7-trihydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy phenanthrene (**2d**) and its 9,10-dihydro derivative (**2e**). Repeated chromatography of this solid using the same solvent system gave pure **2d** (0.03 g) in the early fractions, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 203 °C and **2e** (0.03 g) in the later fractions as a glassy solid.

Further elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) afforded a gummy solid containing a mixture of amplumthrin (**3a**) and flavanthrin (**3c**). Repeated chromatography of this gummy solid with the same eluent gave pure **3a** (0.2 g) in the early fractions as an amorphous solid (Found : C, 67.72; H, 5.66. C₃₄H₃₄O₁₀ requires : C, 67.74; H, 5.69%); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} cm⁻¹ : 3421 (phenolic -OH), 2928, 2848, 1593, 1509, 1457, 1407, 879, 780, 729, 651 and 560 (aromatic nucleus); MS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 602 [M]⁺ (4.0), 337 (9), 314 (7.9), 302 (61.1), 288 (17.8), 255 (20.4), 241 (9.6), 226 (8.9), 212 (10.9), 181 (15.9), 169 (16.1), 129 (16.4), 105 (14.2), 101 (31.6), 91 (50), 82 (62.5), 71 (100) and 57 (73.8).

Acetylation of **3a** with Ac₂O and pyridine in the usual manner gave **3b**, which was purified by chromatography and was obtained as an amorphous solid (Found : C, 65.41; H, 5.47. C₄₂H₄₂O₁₄ requires : C, 65.43; H, 5.50%); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} cm⁻¹ : 2932, 2851, 1768 and 1203 (OAc), 1586, 1506, 1450, 1395, 788, 671, 620 and 522 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.11 (2H, s, H-5 and H-5'), 6.88 (2H, s, H-8 and H-8'), 3.94 (6H, s, OMe at C-3 and C-3'), 3.89 (6H, s, OMe at C-6 and C-6'), 3.83 (6H, s, OMe at C-4 and C-4'), 2.34 (6H, s, OAc at C-7 and C-7'), 2.51–2.54 (4H, m, H₂-9 and H₂-9'), 2.27–2.40 (4H, m, H₂-10 and H₂-10') and 1.99 (6H, s, OAc at C-2 and C-2'). MS : *m/z* (rel. int.) : 770 [M]⁺ (5.4), 728 (8.1), 686 (9.3), 644 (10.2), 602 (12.3), 337 (14.1), 314 (7.5), 302 (65.1), 288 (20.4), 255 (22.5), 241 (10.4), 226 (8.5), 212 (11.0), 181 (20.5), 169 (22.5), 129 (23.0), 105 (18.0), 101 (35.5), 91 (54.5), 82 (60.0), 71 (85.0), 57 (75.0) and 43 (100).

Chromatography of the neutral fraction :

Elution of the column with light petroleum ether gave an uncharacterized oily mass. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) afforded a mixture of Batatasin-III dimethyl ether (**1d**) and β -sitosterol. Repeated chromatography of the above mixture with the same solvent system gave pure **1d** (0.06 g), in the early fractions as a thick oil. The later fractions of the above

rechromatography gave β -sitosterol (0.3 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 138 °C.

Biomimetic synthesis of amplumthrin (3a) and flavanthrin (3c) from 2b and coelonin (2f), respectively, by oxidative phenol-coupling reaction with CuCl(OH). TMEDA :

To 0.1 g of each of **2b** (0.33 mmol) and coelonin (**2f**) (0.41 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (40 ml) were added separately 0.076 g (0.66 mmol) and 0.096 g (0.82 mmol), respectively, of CuCl(OH).TMEDA and the mixtures were separately stirred at room temperature for 4 h in open air. After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure the residues were separately treated with water (25 ml) and extracted with Et₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residues were separately chromatographed. Chromatography of the product obtained from **2b** afforded in the petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate 0.080 g (80%) of amplumthrin (**3a**). Similar chromatography of the product obtained from coelonin (**2f**) gave in the petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate 0.082 g (82%) of flavanthrin (**3c**).

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